

**ASSIGNMENT
ON
INDIAN NATIONAL BIBLIOGRAPHY**

INFORMATION SOURCE AND SERVICES (PRACTICE)

SUBMITTED TO

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INDIAN NATIONAL BIBLIOGRAPHY

Title- Indian National Bibliography
First Published In- 1958(Quarterly)
Latest Published In- May,2017
Publisher- Central Reference Library, Ministry of Education.
Place of Publication- Kolkata
Frequency- Monthly

A National Bibliography reflects cultural heritage of the nation and preserves it for the future generation. It also plays a major tool for national bibliographic control. The Indian National Bibliography is an authoritative bibliographical record of current Indian publications. The INB unit started functions from August 15 1955 in the premises of National Library Kolkata under the Delivery of Books and Newspapers(Public libraries) Act,1954 (Act No. 27 of 1954 as amended by Act No. 99 of 1956).B.S Kesavan was the first National Librarian of independent India. He was also known as the father of Indian national Bibliography.

Between 1958 and 1963 the bibliography was first published as a quarterly and then cumulated annually. Since 1964 it is being published every month and the cumulated every year. But the regularity of the publication has suffered in between for various reasons. There are no publication of INB for the period of 1968, 1969 and 1970. For the period of 1994 to 1999, only annual volumes are being published.

SCOPE

- The aim of INB is to publish accurate and comprehensive bibliographical records of current Indian publications in major fourteen Indian languages(Assamese, Bengali, English, Gujarati, Hindi, Kannada, Malayalam, Marathi, Oriya, Punjabi, Sanskrit, Tamil, Telugu and Urdu).
- INB's objective is to document the nation's published heritage to make the publication known to present and future generation.

- It records the country's intellectual output.
- All publications received in the National Library, Kolkata under the Delivery of Books and Newspapers, (Public Libraries) Act, 1954.

TREATMENT

- The Indian National Bibliography has been conceived as an authoritative bibliographical record of current Indian publications in 14 languages including English received in national library. The following types of publications are excluded:
 - a) Maps
 - b) Musical scores
 - c) Periodicals and Newspapers (except the first issue of a new periodical and the first issue of a periodical under a new title)
 - d) Keys and Guides to Textbooks
 - e) Ephemeral and other such materials.
- In INB Bibliography consist of two parts:-
 - First Part- General Publications.
 - Second Part-Government Publications.

Each part divided into two sections, classified and alphabetical.

- The full information about a book is given in classified section.
- Alphabetical Section contains 'author and title index' and 'subject index'.
- It also provides list of abbreviations and language symbols.
- The main entries are in Roman script and the collations and annotations, if any are in English.

ARRANGEMENT

- INB consists of three parts:-
 - Classified
 - Author & Title Index
 - Subject Index.

The classified portion follows the Dewey Decimal Scheme of classification but the numbers from the colon classification scheme are assigned to each entry at the bottom right hand.

In Author and Title Index, the entries are arranged according to the alphabetical order. When the author of the book is known, it can be traced using Author and Title Index.

In Subject Index to find the books in a particular subject, one can take the help of subject index which is separately printed after the author and title index and then refer to the classified part by the means of DDC Number assigned against the name of the subject.

- INB listed only material received and catalogued by the National Library. All the entries are serially numbered in the classified part.

FORMAT

Printed Version:-

- Every monthly issue cumulated every year within a single volume.
- Information is given in two columns.
- Printing is clear and legible.
- Good quality paper is used.
- It is available in Hardcover binding.

Online-

- Up to May 2000, entries for INB are catalogued manually. The first computerized INB monthly June 2000 came out using TLMS software.
- After the computerisation of compilation of the Indian National Bibliography, it was felt the need to convert the old INB records from 1958 till then. With the approval of the Ministry of Culture, the retro-conversion of INB records was taken up in 2002 and was completed in 2005.
- During this period more than 3 lakhs of multilingual records were converted into MARC 21 format.
- Libsys version iv is used to generate monthly and yearly volumes.
- INDIAN NATIONAL BIBLIOGRAPHY online available at (inbonline.nic.in/). This web site is designed, developed and hosted by National Informatics Centre, Government of India.

- Features like Advance search,Basic search and language search also available.
- Each entry's details given in three views:-
 - Brief View
 - Full View
 - Marc View

SPECIAL FEATURES

- INB is unique when compared with other national bibliographies, since 14 languages come under one umbrella.
- INB provides standardization of bibliographic information. It transliterates the name, according to the language it represents.

DRAWBACKS

- The INB covers only 14 languages including English. The Indian constitution has already recognized 22 languages and also the publication in smaller languages are increasing day by day.
- Characteristics of a national bibliography are that it provides a current,timely,comprehensive and authoritative list of all titles published in a country.In the case of Indian National Bibliography,it is totally depending upon the books received from National Library under the Delivery of Book Act and at present there is no control over the Delivery of Books Act.Some of the publishers are not at all aware of the act and some send their books very late to National Library and it takes minimum three months to reach in the central reference Library.This affects the currency of INB.
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CONCLUSION

A National Bibliography reflects cultural heritage of the nation and preserves it for the future generation.INB should be promoted as the primary, authoritative and up-to-date source of the nation's literary output. It is concluded that the current format used in INB is at par with the international standard and it is very much apt for publishing the language bibliographies and roman bibliography at a time. This was an ambitious project to trace the periodical literature appearing in the Indian language periodicals.

REFERENCES

- <http://inbonline.nic.in/>
- www.connectjournal.com.
- <http://library.ifa.org>.